

A

Family		
low_abundance	(42.05%)	
Siphoviridae	(22.08%)	
Geminiviridae	(8.24%)	
test	(7.05%)	
Myoviridae	(7.05%)	
Steitzviridae	(4.73%)	
Autographiviridae	(4.29%)	
Papillomaviridae	(4.08%)	
Fiersviridae	(3.29%)	
Rhabdoviridae	(2.54%)	
Genomoviridae	(2.44%)	
Picornaviridae	(0.66%)	

B

Genus		
other_family	(78.87%)	
low_abundance	(8.98%)	
test	(7.05%)	
Skunavirus	(1.08%)	
Fromanvirus	(0.71%)	
Pahexavirus	(0.64%)	
Phietavirus	(0.37%)	
Cheoctovirus	(0.31%)	
Ceduovirus	(0.31%)	
Triavirus	(0.25%)	
Dubowvirus	(0.22%)	
Fernvirus	(0.22%)	
Biseqtimavirus	(0.17%)	
Chivirus	(0.17%)	
Jerseyvirus	(0.16%)	
Efquatrovirus	(0.16%)	
Montyvirus	(0.12%)	
Coopervirus	(0.12%)	
Peeveelvirus	(0.1%)	